

**Tenth International Conference
For the Anniversary
of the Balkan Association of Roman
Law and Roman Legal Tradition
“Societas pro Iure Romano”**

IUS & LEX

**University of Sofia “St. Kliment Ohridski”,
Department of Law
September 11th - 13th, 2025**

Book of Abstracts

Sofia, 2025

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Published by:

For Publisher:

Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”,
Faculty of Law

Organizing and Editorial Committee:

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The conference is co- organized by :

Balkan Association of Roman Law and Roman Legal Tradition

“Societas pro Iure Romano” and

Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, Faculty of Law,

Scientific project IUS ROMANUM.

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THE RECEPTION OF ROMAN LAW IN THE PROTECTION OF PROPERTY RIGHTS IN UKRAINE: A HISTORICAL ANALYSIS AND CONTEMPORARY IMPLICATIONS

Abstract: In the context of Europeanisation and the recodification of civil legislation, there is a need to consider ways in which the provisions of the Civil Code of Ukraine on the protection of possession might be improved. One possible inspiration for this could be the conceptual provisions of private law as developed in Ancient Rome. In the spirit of constructive engagement, this study explores the intricacies of property law in the context of ancient Rome (1), current Ukrainian legislation (2), and the evolving landscape of future Ukrainian property laws (3). The aim of this examination is to identify potential avenues for harmonious integration.

Keywords: ownership, reception of roman law, codification of Ukrainian legislation, protection of property rights